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On the possibility of obtaining sodium sulfate from gas cleaning solutions

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Abstract: This article is devoted to the problem of purifying exhaust gases from aluminum production from sulfur compounds. The article shows that the majority of aluminum smelters equipped with electrolyzers with Soderberg anodes have come close to the upper limit of the efficiency of the bell-type shelter and the useful use of gas cleaning equipment. The article discusses single-stage wet gas purification, dry sorption purification of waste gases with alumina in reactors and bag filters, as well as two-stage gas purification systems (including combinations of dry and wet gas purification). To purify gas cleaning solutions from sulfur compounds, a technology has been proposed for the regeneration of sulfur compounds from gas cleaning solutions of electrolysis production using natural cold. This method is based on the known solubility curve of sodium sulfate in aqueous solution. It has been experimentally proven that the proposed technology makes it possible to effectively purify gas cleaning solutions from sulfur compounds.

Key words: sulfur, sulfur emissions, sodium sulfate, aluminum smelter, Soderberg anodes, gas cleaning.

1 Introduction

As is well known, most of the sulfur is released from the electrolyzer as sulfur dioxide emissions. Sulfur emissions from an aluminum smelter with an annual production of 200,000 tons can reach 1,000 tons of sulfur per year [1]. Sulfur gases are known for their detrimental effects on local air quality (particulate matter), rainfall, human health, and global climate [2]. However, sodium sulfide emissions and conversion to sulfate are also considered to be the most important factors in reducing global warming by backscattering solar radiation into space [3, 4].

Cleaning of gases from electrolytic aluminum production has a number of specific features, which are primarily due to the significant volumes of gases being cleaned, the complexity and heterogeneity of their composition. The exhaust electrolysis gases contain carbon oxide and dioxide, hydrogen fluoride, sulfur dioxide, resinous substances, and fine dust. It is clear that with an increase in sulfur concentration, its gross tonnage in the exhaust gases will increase linearly.

The degree of electrolyzer cover characterizes the distribution of gases released during electrolysis between gas cleaning systems and lantern emissions. The efficiency coefficient determines the degree of pollutant capture and depends on the design and technological features of the devices used. The efficiency coefficient is characterized by the ratio of the duration of operation of gas cleaning equipment to the total time of operation and downtime due to accidents and scheduled repairs.

Most aluminum plants equipped with electrolyzers with Soderberg anodes have come very close to the upper limit of the efficiency values of the bell shelter and the useful use of gas cleaning equipment [5].

The use of various schemes and types of gas cleaning equipment at one or another aluminum plant is characterized by approximately the same efficiency, differing only by a few percent. Data on emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere are given in Table 1.

Table 1

Emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere from the electrolysis building [6].

Pollutant	Through the chimneys		Through aeration lanterns	
	g/sec	t/year	g/sec	t/year
Hydrogen fluoride	0.083	2,617	1.51	47.62
Sulfur dioxide	0.271	8,546	0.35	11.04
Carbon monoxide	103,660	3269,0	75.05	2366.7
Inorganic dust	1,332	42.02	11.61	356.13
Benz (a) pyrene	0,00129	0.04068	0.003758	0.11852
Solid fluorides	0.275	8,672	1.03	32.48

Currently, several schemes for cleaning dust and gas mixtures from electrolyzers with self-baking anodes are in operation. In general, the hardware scheme for cleaning anode gases includes bell-shaped covers of electrolyzers, burner devices, under- and inter-housing gas ducts, smoke exhausters, dust and gas cleaning units (electrostatic filters and/or wet cleaning devices), cyclone-mist collectors, and smoke stacks [7].

There are also other schemes for capturing exhaust gases. In particular, a number of electrolysis buildings use single-stage wet gas cleaning; the use of dry sorption cleaning of exhaust gases with alumina in reactors and bag filters is also known, as well as two-stage gas cleaning systems (including a combination of dry and wet gas cleaning) [8].

Methods

In one of the aluminium productions on a semi-industrial scale, a technology for regenerating sulphur compounds from gas cleaning solutions of electrolysis production using natural cold was introduced. This method is based on the known solubility curve of sodium sulphate in an aqueous solution – Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Solubility of sodium sulfate in water.

Analysis of the curve in Fig. 1 shows that the use of natural cold allows the formation and precipitation of sodium sulfate crystals from saturated gas cleaning solutions. The scheme shown in Fig. 2 was proposed for the implementation of a semi-industrial test.

The pilot plant diagram (Fig. 2) includes a mixing tank, a thickener-separator, a box with a grid and a pipeline system for transporting clarified (initial) and desulfated solutions, as well as the thickened product. A temperature sensor is installed in the mixing tank.

Pilot industrial tests were conducted to determine the efficiency of the implementation of the equipment and process flow diagram for crystallization of sodium sulfate from gas cleaning solutions using natural cold to obtain a commercial product, the purpose of which was:

- determination of the fundamental possibility of obtaining sodium sulfate of proper quality;
- clarification of technological process parameters;
- production of a pilot batch of sodium sulfate for the consumer.

Fig. 2. Scheme of a pilot-scale plant for crystallization of sodium sulfate from GOU solutions.

The gas cleaning solution was used as the feedstock for obtaining crystalline sodium sulfate, and natural cold air served as the cooling agent. The clarified GOU solution was poured into the mixing tank in a volume of 5-6 m³ with a temperature from +40 0C to +44 °C. The cooling of the solution continued from 2 to 3 days, since the outside air temperature fluctuated from -3 °C to - 17 °C. Pumping of solutions, filtration and delivery of crystalline sodium sulfate to the cryolite drying unit occurred within 2 hours.

Results

As a result of pilot industrial tests, four technological cycles of sodium sulfate crystallization from GOU solutions were conducted. Three batches of crystalline product were obtained. Samples of the initial and obtained products were analyzed, and the temperature of the outside air and cooled solutions, the time of solution cooling and filtration were also recorded.

Table 2. Chemical composition of the obtained crystalline sodium sulfate

	Elements to be determined, %				
	F	Na ₂ SO ₄	Na ₂ CO ₃	Fe	Solid residue
cycle 1 Na ₂ SO ₄	0.4	96.9	2.1	0.002	0.42
cycle 2 Na ₂ SO ₄	0.3	96.5	2.2	0.002	0.22
cycle 3 Na ₂ SO ₄	0.3	95.3	2.9	0.002	0.9

Comparison of the chemical composition of desulfated solutions shows that the degree of sodium sulfate extraction from GOU solutions is within 36-68%. This depends on the cooling temperature of the solutions and the initial chemical composition. In general, it can be stated that reaching a temperature of 4 °C in the GOU solution is sufficient for its regeneration from sulfur compounds and the formation of crystalline sodium sulfate (Fig. 3). Accordingly, the regulating parameter (due to the impossibility of influencing the ambient temperature) is the cooling time of the solution in a container located outside and the temperature of the atmospheric air. There is an option to intensify the process by installing refrigeration equipment, but this will lead to an increase in the cost of the process.

Fig. 3. Appearance of the obtained sodium sulfate

The composition of the solution after crystallization of sodium sulfate changes insignificantly, the concentration of the main chemical elements - Na₂CO₃, NaHCO₃, NaF corresponds to the regulations of the clarified solution sent to the crystallization process of regeneration cryolite and/or calcium fluoride for its own needs.

Discussion

It has been established experimentally that for 1 cycle (2-3 hours) of the turnover of the GOU solutions "mixed solution on GOU - saturated solution with GOU" in the regeneration process, the concentration of sodium sulfate increases to 20 g / l. Consequently, the mother liquors after crystallization of regeneration cryolite with a concentration of Na₂SO₄ of 40 g / l and less can circulate in the system "preparation of mixed solution - solution on GOU - cryolite production" without being removed from the process and discharged to the sludge field, which is necessary to maintain the balance of sulfur products in soda solutions. In this case, the savings on soda ash will

amount to 8,000 - 10,000 tons / year for one enterprise, increase the service life of sludge fields and allow obtaining marketable products.

Table 2 shows the chemical composition of crystalline sodium sulfate obtained at different concentrations of chemical compounds in the solution. The content of the main substance - sodium sulfate - in the product is from 95.3% to 96.9%, which confirms the dependence of the efficiency of the crystallization process on the temperature of the solution and its chemical composition. Impurities in the obtained product include a small content of fluorine and solid residue (less than 1%).

Conclusion

1. The interaction of gas cleaning solutions with lime was studied, and it was shown that lime can be used to regenerate gas cleaning solutions from sulfur compounds.

2. The process of crystallization of sodium sulfate from gas cleaning solutions using atmospheric air as a coolant in the cold period of the year was studied, industrial-grade sodium sulfate was obtained. It was shown that the use of natural cold allows for effective regeneration of gas cleaning solutions from sulfur compounds.

3. The chemical composition of the obtained sodium sulfate allows us to talk about its possible use in related industries, for example, in the production of cellulose, construction or the production of synthetic detergents.

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